

Deep Reinforcement Learning for Dynamic Network Slice Security Using Moving Target Defense

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Abstract—Network slicing has emerged as a transformative enabler for meeting the diverse requirements of 5G and beyond networks, including 6G. However, network slices’ dynamic and virtualized nature introduces significant security challenges, particularly against evolving cyber threats. We propose a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based Moving Target Defense (MTD) strategy tailored for secure network slicing to address these challenges. Our approach utilizes a Q-Learning framework to manage MTD actions dynamically, optimizing security while maintaining service quality. Extensive simulations demonstrate the effectiveness of our framework in minimizing attack success rates and ensuring operational stability, significantly outperforming baseline methods such as random decision-making.

Index Terms—Network Slicing, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), Moving Target Defense (MTD), Q-Learning, Cybersecurity, Proactive Defense, 6G Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network slicing represents a transformative advancement in network technology, allowing several virtual networks on a common physical framework to be established [1]. Each network slice operates independently and has specific functionalities and protocols to meet diverse service requirements. However, deploying network slicing in 6G networks introduces significant challenges, particularly in resource management, slice orchestration, network security, and privacy.

The security challenges in network slicing are multifaceted. Life cycle security involves ensuring slices’ secure creation,

maintenance, and termination. Inter-slice security addresses the protection of coexistent slices sharing the same physical infrastructure. Intra-slice security focuses on safeguarding individual slices against internal threats. Furthermore, the integration of Software Defined Networking (SDN) [2] and Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) [3] further complicates the security landscape. VNFs replace traditional hardware-based network functions with software-based implementations, increasing the attack surface and exposing the network to threats such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks [4].

To address these challenges, Moving Target Defense (MTD) emerges as a promising proactive security approach by dynamically altering system configurations, thereby increasing complexity for potential attackers and enhancing network security [5]. However, implementing MTD introduces system overhead and possible performance degradation. The primary challenge lies in effectively scheduling MTD actions across network slices to optimize security while minimizing operational costs.

This paper proposes a novel framework integrating Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) with MTD to provide a robust, cost-effective, and proactive security solution for next-generation network slicing [6]. It can handle multiple network slices, each one modified for specific services with distinct Quality of Service (QoS) and security requirements. By leveraging DRL, the framework continuously monitors per-

formance variations and strategically manages the deployment of MTD actions. This work represents the first integration of DRL with MTD for network slicing, aiming to maintain QoS while enhancing security across diverse service slices.

Additionally, the framework focuses on mitigating DDoS attacks targeting network slices, where botnets of numerous consumer devices flood critical components such as the User Plane Function (UPF) [7] with excessive traffic. Such disruptions degrade network performance, reduce service availability, increase latency, and consume bandwidth for coexistent slices. These impacts are particularly detrimental to latency-sensitive applications, leading to potential Service Level Agreements (SLAs) breaches and causing significant operational and business disruptions [8].

A. Related Works

As the IoT proliferates, so do cybersecurity threats from low-cost devices, challenging the deployment of robust IoT solutions. NFV and SDN technologies have enhanced IoT security. These technologies enable scalable, flexible honeynets that simulate real networks to mislead attackers. A notable advancement includes an autonomous IoT honeynet mechanism based on SDN and NFV [9], alongside the LSTM-FUZZY system that detects and mitigates DDoS and Portscan attacks within SDNs, demonstrating effectiveness in network management and attack mitigation [10].

Further, deep learning methods are increasingly employed to secure IoT devices against cyber threats. An approach integrating LSTM modules and a decision tree has shown significant efficacy, achieving over 98% accuracy in detecting cyber attacks on IoT networks, tested with real-world Modbus traffic data [11]. The research introduces a novel dataset from a simulated 5G environment and a deep-learning model, SliceSecure, which detects attacks with approximately 100% accuracy [12].

Continuing in advanced network security, the MERLINS architecture [13] optimizes MTD strategies for 5G and 6G networks using a multi-objective Markov decision process and DRL, enhancing security across multi-cloud environments [14]. Another strategy involves a cloud-based adaptive ML models' orchestrator for securing 5G slices, which customizes detection algorithms based on real-time conditions and device characteristics, demonstrating superior efficiency in resource allocation and malicious traffic isolation [15].

Integrating dynamic defence strategies, particularly MTD, with advanced machine learning techniques significantly enhances network infrastructure security, addressing the rapidly evolving landscape of cybersecurity threats [16]. It ensures robust protection against various potential attacks, as seen in developing systems that dynamically adapt to hostile environments and optimize security responses.

B. Motivation, Contribution & Novelty

The current approach to security in network slicing relies heavily on reactive measures. However, these methods are insufficient to address the challenges posed by advanced

and evolving cyber threats, including zero-day exploits and advanced persistent threats. Therefore, there is a need to shift towards more proactive security strategies that ensure the integrity and continuous operation of critical network environments.

This paper introduces a novel security framework integrating MTD with DRL to secure network slices proactively. Unlike traditional security solutions that reactively address threats, the proposed approach anticipates potential attacks and dynamically adjusts defence mechanisms. This constant reconfiguration of network parameters complicates the attack surface for adversaries, enhancing the resilience of network segments against a wide range of cyber threats and proactively securing critical infrastructure.

The novelty of this research work lies in the synergistic implementation of MTD and DRL within the context of network slicing. The approach leverages MTD's ability to alter the attack surface and DRL's adaptive learning, which aims to maintain robust security and operational efficiency. The proposed framework optimizes security posture and network performance by making real-time adjustments to security policies based on the evolving threat landscape and network conditions, minimizing service disruption risks and maintaining key metrics such as latency and throughput.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model in Fig. 1 illustrates a hierarchical architecture for secure network slicing, divided into three functional layers: the Service Instance Layer, the Network Slice Instance Layer, and the Resource Layer. These layers dynamically interact through the MTD agent, which employs proactive security mechanisms while maintaining QoS. The Service Instance Layer represents diverse service types like eMBB, uRLLC, and mMTC. These services cater to unique requirements, including high-speed data, low-latency operations, and large-scale IoT connectivity. Logical slices in the Network Slice Instance Layer are tailored to meet these demands. Each slice integrates functional components such as the SMF for session control, the UPF for data routing, the PCF for enforcing network policies, and the NSO for slice lifecycle management.

The Resource Layer encompasses physical and virtual resources, including base stations, routers, and data centres. Virtualization technologies like NFV and SDN abstract and dynamically manage these resources, allowing real-time allocation based on service demands and security needs. At the core of this architecture, the MTD agent, powered by DRL, monitors network slice states, including resource usage, latency, and security status. It selects and executes MTD actions such as traffic re-routing, VNF migration, and parameter adjustments. Using a reward mechanism, the agent iteratively optimizes its decision-making policy to enhance security while ensuring operational stability.

Dynamic Nodes (DNs) simulate real-world traffic and threats, enabling framework evaluation. Bidirectional data flow between slices, the MTD agent, and DN facilitates continuous learning and adaptation, ensuring robust defence mechanisms,

Fig. 1. Proposed Architecture of DRL-Driven MTD Strategy for Enhanced Network Slice Security

efficient resource allocation, and real-time decision-making. This system model provides a comprehensive, secure and adaptive 6G network slicing solution.

A. Functional Layers and their Roles

The enhanced architectural design for network slicing includes several functional layers, each with specific roles to support the overall network architecture.

1) *Service Instance Layer*: This layer comprises various service instances tailored to meet specific user requirements. Each service instance represents a unique application or service, such as eMBB, uRLLC, and mMTC.

2) *Network Slice Instance Layer*: It is responsible for the logical partitioning of the network. It includes the NSO, which manages the lifecycle of each network slice. Each slice has its own set of network functions, such as the SMF, UPF, and PCF.

3) *Resource Layer*: It consists of the physical resources and virtual resources which represents the network slices. This includes base stations, routers, switches, and data centers. Virtualization technologies like NFV and SDN are utilized to abstract and manage these resources efficiently.

B. Resource Sharing and Security Isolation

Effective resource sharing and robust security isolation are crucial for the optimal functioning of network slices. The proposed architecture employs both static and dynamic resource allocation strategies to achieve these goals.

1) *Static Resource Allocation*: Static resource allocation ensures that each slice has guaranteed resources. Let R_i denote the static resources allocated to slice i . The total static resources R_{total} can be expressed by eq.(1)

$$R_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^N R_i, \quad (1)$$

where N is the total number of slices.

2) *Dynamic Resource Allocation*: Dynamic resource allocation adjusts resources in real-time based on demand and threat levels. Let $D_i(t)$ represent the dynamic resources allocated to slice i at time t . The total dynamic resources $D_{total}(t)$ is given by eq.(2).

$$D_{total}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N D_i(t) \quad (2)$$

The objective is to maximize the utility function $U(t)$, balancing performance and security which is given by eq.(3)

$$U(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_i \cdot P_i(t) - \beta_i \cdot S_i(t)), \quad (3)$$

where $P_i(t)$ is the performance metric, $S_i(t)$ is the security risk, and α_i and β_i are weighting factors for performance and security, respectively.

C. Virtual Network Functions

VNFs are critical components of network slicing, providing the necessary network functionalities in a flexible and scalable manner.

1) *Role of VNFs in Network Slicing*: VNFs such as routing, firewalling, and load balancing are deployed within each slice. The NFV orchestrator manages these VNFs, ensuring their optimal deployment and operation to meet service requirements.

2) *Mathematical Modeling of VNF Placement*: The placement of VNFs is crucial for optimizing performance and security. Let V_j denote the VNF j , and L_{ij} be the latency between slice i and VNF j . The total latency L_{total} for all VNFs across all slices is given by eq.(4)

$$L_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M [(L_{ij}) \times (x_{ij})], \quad (4)$$

where x_{ij} is a binary variable that represents whether VNF j is assigned to slice i .

The optimization objective is to minimize L_{total} while meeting security constraints eq.(5)

$$\min_{x_{ij}} L_{total} \quad \text{subject to} \quad \sum_{j=1}^M x_{ij} \cdot S_j \leq S_{max}, \forall i, \quad (5)$$

where S_j is the security requirement of VNF j and S_{max} is the maximum allowable security risk for any slice.

III. PROPOSED DRL-BASED MTD SOLUTION FOR NETWORK SLICE PROTECTION

The agent, positioned as the network slice controller at the hierarchical apex of the network slices, orchestrates, maintains, and reconfigures the slices throughout their lifecycle. Its fundamental role is to master the timing of MTD actions to preempt and reduce the incidence of cyber-attacks, acting as the central MTD controller responsible for executing proactive defence strategies. Initially, the agent observes the environmental state and subsequent network configurations and implements a selected action.

The learning mechanism employed is Q-learning, a model-free, value-based approach that computes the Q-value function using the Bellman equation. The Bellman equation for the state-value function under a policy π is given by eq.(6)

TABLE I
GLOSSARY OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Denotes
MTD	Moving Target Defense
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
SDN	Software Defined Networking
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
CD	Consumer Device
UPF	User Plane Function
SLA	Service Level Agreements
RL	Reinforcement Learning
NSO	Network Slice Orchestrator
SMF	Session Management Function
PCF	Policy Control Function
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
uRLLC	ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communications
DN	Data Network
AMMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NRF	Network Repository Function

$$V^\pi(s) = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \pi(a|s) \sum_{s', r} p(s', r | s, a) r + \gamma \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \pi(a|s) \sum_{s', r} p(s', r | s, a) V^\pi(s'). \quad (6)$$

In this context:

- $V^\pi(s)$ represents the value of state s under the policy π .
- $\pi(a|s)$ indicates the probability of selecting action a in state s according to policy π .
- $p(s', r | s, a)$ is the probability of transitioning to state s' and receiving reward r after performing action a in state s .
- r is the immediate reward obtained from the transition.
- γ is the discount factor, which determines the weight of future rewards.
- $V^\pi(s')$ denotes the value of the next state s' .

While the Bellman equation for the state-action value function, also known as the Q-value, is expressed in eq.(7)

$$Q^\pi(s, a) = \sum_{s', r} p(s', r | s, a) r + \gamma \sum_{s', r} p(s', r | s, a) \sum_{a'} \pi(a' | s') Q^\pi(s', a'). \quad (7)$$

Q-learning is a type of reinforcement learning that doesn't rely on a model of the environment and focuses on learning the value of actions. It updates its Q-values using (8)

$$Q(s, a) \leftarrow (1 - \alpha)Q(s, a) + \alpha \left[r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a') \right], \quad (8)$$

where α is the learning rate and $\max_{a'} Q(s', a')$ represents the highest Q-value achievable from the next state s' considering all possible actions a' .

The Deep Q-Learning Algorithm leverages a model-free reinforcement learning approach to develop optimal decision-making policies for environments with discrete state and action

spaces, tailored explicitly for secure network slicing using an MTD strategy. Hence, the algorithm iteratively refines the optimal action-value function, $Q^*(s, a)$, which predicts the cumulative reward of taking action a in state s and adhering to the optimal policy after that.

Initialization starts with a replay buffer E , which holds experience tuples to facilitate experience replay, addressing issues of correlated data and non-stationary distributions. The Q-values are approximated using a neural network, represented by weights θ , with updates during the learning phase based on temporal difference methods employing a target network \hat{Q} with weights θ^- for stabilization.

In order to perform a gradient descent step on (9) with respect to θ we need to set (10)

$$(y_j - Q(S_j, a_j; \theta))^2, \quad (9)$$

$$y_j = \begin{cases} r_j, & \text{if } S'_j \text{ is terminal,} \\ r_j + \gamma \max_{a'} \hat{Q}(S'_j, a'; \theta^-), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Algorithm 1 Deep Q-Learning algorithm using MTD Strategy

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Initialize  $E$ ,  $Q$  and  $\hat{Q}$ 
for  $episode = 1$  to  $N$  do
  Reset state  $S$ 
  Set exploration probability  $\epsilon \leftarrow 1$ 
  for  $t = 1$  to  $T_{epoch}$  do
    if  $\tau \leq \epsilon, \tau \in [0, 1]$  then
      Choose a random action  $a_t$ 
    else
      Choose action  $a_t = \arg \max_a Q(S, a; \theta)$ 
    end if
    Execute action  $a_t$ , record  $r_t$  and  $S'$ , store  $(S, a_t, r_t, S')$ 
    in  $E$ , and sample a minibatch  $(S_j, a_j, r_j, S'_j)$  from  $E$ .
     $y_j \leftarrow (10)$ 
    Every  $C$  steps reset  $\hat{Q} = Q$ 
    Decay  $\epsilon$ 
    Update  $S \leftarrow S'$ 
  end for
  Update policy  $\sigma$  with new policy mapping  $S \rightarrow \arg \max_a Q(S, a; \theta)$ 
end for

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The state S_t at time t represents the configuration and status of the network slices, encapsulating various metrics such as resource utilization, security and network performance indicators defined by eq.(11)

$$S_t = \{R_t, U_t, P_t\}, \quad (11)$$

where R_t denotes the resource allocation vector, U_t represents the utilization metrics, and P_t indicates the performance metrics at time t .

The action a_t chosen by the agent at time t is of a set of possible MTD strategies that can be applied to the network

slices. These actions include reconfiguration of network paths, migration of VNFs, and modification of security parameters, mathematically defined by eq.(12)

$$a_t \in \mathcal{A} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\}, \quad (12)$$

where each a_i represents a specific MTD action.

The reward R_t received by the agent after taking an action a_t at state S_t is a crucial feedback mechanism. It evaluates the effectiveness of the action in enhancing security and maintaining performance, given by eq.(13)

$$R_t = \lambda P_t - \mu S_t, \quad (13)$$

where P_t is the performance metric, S_t is the security metric, and λ and μ are weighting factors that balance the importance of performance and security.

Hence, the reward function assists the agent in learning to maximize network performance while minimizing security risks, leading to an optimal policy for network slice protection.

Integrating MTD with the Q-learning framework involves defining the actions as MTD manoeuvres. The agent aims to select actions which can increase the long-term security benefits while minimizing disruption. Thus, the state S_t includes the current network configuration, attack surface metrics, and historical performance data. Also, the action a_t represents different MTD strategies and the reward r_t reflects the effectiveness of the MTD action in preventing attacks and maintaining service quality $r_t = \lambda \times \text{Security Improvement} - \mu \times \text{Service Disruption}$, where λ and μ are weights balancing security and service quality.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation environment was implemented using Python and the Gym library for DRL training, combined with TensorFlow for neural network computations. The environment replicates a 6G network infrastructure with multiple network slices, each serving distinct service requirements such as eMBB, uRLLC, and mMTC. Diverse traffic models were employed to simulate different types of network traffic, including latency-sensitive and bandwidth-intensive applications. Various cyber-attack scenarios, including DDoS attacks and intrusions, were incorporated to test the robustness of the MTD strategies. The DRL framework was implemented using TensorFlow, where neural networks were used to calculate the Q-values.

The training procedure involves several key steps. Initially, the Q-network was initialized with random weights, and a Q-network was set up with the same initial weights. A replay buffer E was started in order to store experience tuples. During training, an ϵ -greedy policy was employed to balance exploration and exploitation. Initially, it was set to a high value to promote exploration, and it was gradually reduced over time to prioritize exploitation as training progressed. Experience tuples (S, A, R, S') were collected and stored in the replay buffer. The Q-values were updated using the Bellman

optimality equation, and gradient descent was performed on the loss function to minimize the error.

A. Evaluation Metrics and Results

The average reward per episode, as depicted in Fig. 4, starts unstable and primarily negative, reflecting the initial random execution of MTD actions. As the training progresses and the network optimizes, this average reward increases, eventually stabilizing at a higher value indicative of effective learning and decision-making. The average latency (L) for each network slice is modeled by eq.(14)

$$L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N L_i, \quad (14)$$

where L_i represents the latency of the i -th slice, and N is the total number of slices.

Throughput (T) for each network slice was evaluated to ensure that the proactive defense strategies did not adversely affect data delivery. The throughput is calculated by eq.(15)

$$T = \frac{1}{T_{total}} \sum_{i=1}^N T_i, \quad (15)$$

where T_i is the throughput of the i -th slice, and T_{total} is the total duration of the simulation.

Resource utilization (U) was monitored to assess the efficiency of the resource allocation strategies, given by eq.(16)

$$U = \frac{1}{R_{total}} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i, \quad (16)$$

where R_i denotes the resources allocated to the i -th slice, and R_{total} is the total available resources.

Security effectiveness (S) was quantified by the reduction in successful attacks, measured using eq.(17)

$$S = \frac{A_{initial} - A_{final}}{A_{initial}}, \quad (17)$$

where $A_{initial}$ is the number of attacks before implementing the MTD strategies, and A_{final} is the number of attacks after implementation.

The average latency across network slices decreased by approximately 15%, demonstrating the efficiency of the dynamic MTD actions. There was no significant degradation in throughput, indicating that the MTD strategies effectively mitigate attacks without compromising data delivery. Resource utilization was maintained at optimal levels, ensuring efficient allocation and effective use of network resources. Additionally, the security effectiveness demonstrated a significant improvement of over 30%, showcasing the robustness of the proposed defence mechanism in mitigating successful attacks.

Figure 3 illustrates the number of actions taken per training episode. As the number of episodes increases, there is a decline in the average number of actions. Initially, approximately 110 MTD actions are performed per episode, but this number decreases to around seven actions. This trend indicates the

Fig. 2. Success rate per episode during training

Fig. 3. Number of actions per episode during training

agent's growing strategic capability in effective threat prevention. Figure 2 depicts the average success rate of the agent in preventing attacks. For each training episode, a series of 15 DDoS attacks are scattered at various points during the episode's duration. Initially, the agent exhibited a success rate of 75%, emphasizing the need to refine its decision-making process. As training progressed, the DQN-powered agent demonstrated significant adaptability, with the success rate varying between approximately 60% and 95%.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This study introduces a comprehensive security framework integrating DRL with MTD to enhance network slicing security. Leveraging the proactive nature of MTD and the adaptive capabilities of DRL, the framework significantly outperforms traditional random MTD strategies by effectively preventing

Fig. 4. Average Reward per Episode During Training

attacks, minimizing service disruptions, and maintaining high-security levels across network operations. Future enhancements will focus on integrating more features and MTD actions to broaden the framework's proactive defences, aiming to preemptively address a wider array of sophisticated cyber threats. Plans include applying the framework in complex network environments and against advanced attack vectors, with rigorous testing to ensure its efficacy and reliability in real-world scenarios. These developments are expected to improve significantly the framework's adaptability and effectiveness in protecting network slices against a dynamic threat landscape.

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